

CONGRESS BUILDING RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

RESUPERES European project. Multiplier Event

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Presentation

According to recent studies, the first five years of a teacher's career can be a time of particular vulnerability, with estimates of 40-50% of early-career teachers in many countries leaving the profession during that time.

Studies exploring why teachers leave have pointed to teacher stress and burnout and inadequate pre-service preparation for the reality of teachers' work.

It is reported that 33% of Norwegian teachers who started teaching in municipalities and counties (school owners) in 2006 had left the profession by 2011. Furthermore, 40% of the graduates of Norwegian postgraduate teacher education programmes did not start teaching or left within 18 months.

With this type of scientific event, the aim is to discuss and empower resilience in current and future teachers. To this end, the European RESUPERES project 2021-1-ES01-KA220-HED 000031173: "RESUPERES Intervention Proposal for the Development of Resilience in Higher Education" will be presented. Participants will also have the opportunity to learn from other resilience projects and their results.

The said congress will have a day dedicated to the dissemination of the RESUPERES: manual, website, interactive platform, and toolkit through a series of conferences and theoretical-practical activities after the pilot study activity has been developed.

You can learn more about the project [here](#).

CONGRESS BUILDING RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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INAUGURAL CONFERENCE

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the European Union

A Dream Under Construction: RESUPERES PROJECT: Intervention proposal for Resilience development in Higher Education. Overcoming Adversity.

Carolina Sousa

Scientific Coordinator of the RESUPERES Project – Portugal

**HOGSKULEN PA VESTLANDET - Western Norway University of
Applied Sciences (HVL), Bergen, Norway**

(RESUPERES European project. Multiplier Event)

25th of MAY 2023

Co-funded by
the European Union

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To what extent is it not important to have personal and professional knowledge of a teacher, a student, who deals with the ambiguity of educational situations, with a view to an education that seeks the new challenges we face today, in our society?

► Some questions arise in intervention with resilience competencies...

**To what extent does access to a quality life not require, in every student and teacher, a process favoring progressive autonomy and self-determination, in the emotional, sports, health, educational, social, communication, arts, cultural, and other fields so important to carry on a project like this one, in resilience competencies in higher education?
the RESUPERES project?**

The study of higher education between Portugal and Spain, universities of the Algarve and Granada, dates back many years, since the day where we met and talked about this topic: Resilience.

○ And it is from a joint reflection on the importance that higher education assumes in our two countries, that the dream begins, a dream with the both General Coordinators of this project, from the University of Granada, Professor Mar Cepero Gonzalez and Professor Francisco Javier Rojas to carry out a project that could frame some of the issues underlying the theoretical constellation that fits into the notion of resilience.

In the sense of its promotion, in order to help students and teachers to rethink the theme from new angles, and deepen their potential in order to contribute to its promotion and with emphasis on improving the quality of life and the personal, academic, motivational and emotional training of students and teachers.

RESUPERES has its roots..

Effectively, a dream is - in many situations - interconnected with the life trajectory of those who experience it.

And RESUPERES has its roots in the research initiated in the last century by Carolina who turned out to be an expert – related to her story of life - on the theme which leads us to think and reflect that an investigation, in this case, the research on Resilience, is always part of a life story because a life story always involves multiple determinants of the choices and decision making that personal and professional development requires.

And RESUPERES is a life story of Carolina, Mar and Javier, who dreamed a project under construction with creativity, motivation, commitment, rigor, trust, innovation, solidarity, friendship, and research.

The Importance of Dreaming

Several investigations have shown the importance of sleep in the consolidation of memory and in the integration of novel content in those already known.

And our dream is under construction between the 3 of us, for several years.

**Let's all remember that the goal of
resilience (the subject of our dream
under construction)**

is

to build more humane worlds."

(Forés and Grané, 2010).

RESUPERES: A Dream Under Construction.

**So, it was decided that an application would be prepared, to produce relevant, international, indispensable social knowledge for the realization of a great goal sustained in our dream under construction:
The RESUPERES PROJECT.**

And we dreamt of a professional intervention to build and strengthen resilience, which requires **not only** a holistic and integrative understanding of the factors, dynamics, and circumstances that facilitate and enhance it, **but also**, always considering the ethical dimension and respect for fundamental human rights.

RESUPERES: The Dream...

Research on resilience motivates us to carry out professional interventions that promote relational and participatory processes that help to resignify and transform adverse situations of students and teachers, in a healthy and integral way, aiming at well-being and increasing their quality of life.

The ability to overcome adversity

Indeed, universities are determining environments for individuals to develop the ability to overcome adversity, adapt to the pressures and situations they face, and acquire the social, academic, and vocational skills necessary for life.

Thus, the educational institution must become a place that provides security and promotes positive learning environments and harmony, both among its students and teachers.

Our goal with this dream under construction...

It is our goal that with this dream we can not only reflect and give visibility to some of the new knowledge that emerges *from* and *in* the research on Resilience, but also, better understand and deepen the concept of resilience, a concept of interactive and multidimensional character.

Carolina Sousa

Educação para a Resiliência

Carolina Sousa

Trauma, contexto y exclusión Promocionando Resiliencia

Antonio Salvador Jiménez Hernández
Carolina Silva Sousa
(Coordinadores)

Prólogo de
Isabel M^a Bernedo Muñoz

GEU
EDITORIAL

Colección
INFANCIA,
CULTURA Y
EDUCACIÓN

3

The history of humanity and throughout its growth, has been characterized by a constant struggle to survive, finding itself in the face of circumstances of wars, and climate changes, from the prelude to the evolution of man, rethinking the circumstances and through them, create new scenarios to continue.

Today, the struggle is of an expansive order, war, poverty, solitude, etc

RESILIENCE

A couple of questions from a reporter - Porto Alegre, Brasil

What is the resilience in higher Education?

Resilience is the capacity of human beings to face adversity, to adapt and overcome tragedies, traumas, threats or severe stress.

Why is it important for teacher activity to develop this capacity?

Resilience involves a series of behaviors and ways of thinking that anyone can learn and develop as another area of their Education.

The concept of resilience

It was introduced in Psychology by Michael Rutter in 1986 and popularized by Boris Cyrulnik (Nineteen ninety-nine), who is considered the father of resilience for working on those concepts from his own experience, grew up in orphanages and survived a concentration camp.

Cyrulnik (2002) defines resilience as the ability to overcome tragedies by knowing how to integrate those experiences to live satisfactorily.

Another journalist asked me:
why is it important in a teacher's
activity to develop the capacity for
resilience?

To which I replied...

We are all aware of the current difficulties inherent to educational activities, particularly when the areas of teacher training are characterized by anthropological, cultural, ethical, and axiological multidimensionality, which makes the process of elaboration of a specific theoretical body and its sharing, as a strategy that is both complex and seductive, but difficult to carry out.

For classical psychology, resilience is related to the ability to recover from emotional crises.

For positive psychology, resilience is the ability to recover and post-traumatic growth.

Resilience? For psychology

In recent years, resilience has begun to be the subject of research in various disciplines: Physics, Health, Medicine, Social Sciences, Education, etc. Studies on the subject show trends that we could classify into three schools:

Among the three schools, there are differences in the way of understanding the concepts of vulnerability, risk, and adversity, which has resulted in differences in the understanding of how resilience occurs and what are the recommendations to promote it.

In Europe, Resilience has been related to the concept of post-traumatic growth by understanding Resilience simultaneously

such as the ability to emerge unscathed from an adverse experience and use it to learn and improve.

**Considers that to have resilience it is necessary:
to have good self-esteem,
empathy,
humour,
and support from someone significant.**

The Resilience in the American Continent?

In America, Resilience refers to the coping process that helps a person to remain intact.

It seeks to determine social conditions, group relations, cultural manifestations, and community values that ultimately form the basis of a process of collective resilience.

In summary of these schools

In one way or another, Resilience research aims to determine why some people manage to learn from their experiences and even find benefits in them, even when they are very adverse and to do so by studying the whole process and the variables involved in it.

And teachers are expected to be emotionally stable, with high motivation to succeed, frustration tolerance, humour, passion for their teaching work.

According to neuroscience, resilience is the ability to face an adverse situation, overcome it and emerge stronger.

A resilient mindset prepares a person to cope with future change and adversity, enhances the ability to adapt to change, and facilitates personal growth.

RESILIENCE

Resilience is potentially present in each of us, but it is differentially determined according to the stages of psychological development, the life cycle, and environmental conditions.

From the perspective of inclusive higher education, it is essential to highlight the work of university teachers, who must favour the approach to issues that allow them to face problems, with a critical and positive attitude to overcome any adversity.

Sousa (2021)

Resilience in Higher Education

In the end, Resilience

Is a concept that today is of eminent importance in the development of the education of children, youth and adults, and social groups at high risk or subject to high levels of stress, it is a concept that rather than an innovation in education, represents a resume of an interest in an existing but neglected reality.

There is an intimate relationship between the process of resilience and the life cycle of the person confronted with adversity. We will refer to any adversity, be it cognitive, sensory, or motor, as resilience is present in any of them due to multiple factors such as:

social misunderstanding,

discrimination,

or miscommunication.

And from an initial dream, initially shared by 3 teachers

A project under construction is born and that presents itself as a challenging task, so many and so complex are the dimensions implied in it, which we immediately begin to present to all of you.

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RESUPERES

INTERVENTION PROPOSAL FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION. OVERCOMING ADVERSITIES.

KA220-HED-Higher
Education
Partnerships 2021

RESUPEERS: GENERAL OBJECTIVE

Analyse, design, and evaluate an Intervention Programme in the educational context of Higher Education, developing the constructs of resilience, such as coping, self-concept, self-esteem, leadership, etc., and based on competencies within the areas of health (corporal expression, inner gymnastics, mindfulness, yoga, physical education, and sports), the digital world and communication, the performing and visual arts and culture, emotion which generates resilient behavioral patterns.

Related to Intellectual Outcomes (O),
Multiplier Events (E),
and Activities (C):

Create a RESUPERES MANUAL in Higher Education.

Implement a WEBSITE, as a multilingual e-learning platform, for online training (O2).

PILOT STUDY OF THE RESUPERES PROJECT (C2-C6):

Design, apply and evaluate an implementation plan of activities such as Soft Skills, Coping Strategies, etc., focused on the improvement of resilient competencies, using both internationalization (5 European universities) and work from different areas (cultural, artistic, virtual, communicative, dramatic and sports activities), as a Pilot Study (C2 to C6, RT5).

RESUPERES SPREAD "DIFFUSE": Design, create and disseminate Intellectual Products for resilience work: online digital platform, resilience toolkit, videos, virtual tours, etc.

APP RESUPERES: Create a RESUPERES App, to work with autonomy and to serve as a support and methodological resource for Resilient training in Higher Education .

CREATE SUBJECT: Assess the global effect of the program (on the entire educational community), create an itinerary, and therefore a subject for the development and improvement of resilience in university educational contexts.

IMPLEMENTATION OF ACTIVITIES C7-C11: Develop and implement a RESUPERES subject in each of the participating universities, and evaluate the implementation of the RESUPERES pathway in the partner universities (C7 to C11).

RESILIENCE INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS: Disseminate all the results provided by the RESUPERES Project, to establish a RESUPERES pathway in university education .

RESUPERES: Countries

**RESUPERES
includes the
universities**

**UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA
(Spain –coordinating
institution)**

**UNIVERSIDADE DO ALGARVE ,
(PORTUGAL, FARO)**

**UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI SUOR
ORSOLA BENINCASA (ITALIA,
NAPOLI)**

**UNIVERZITET U BEOGRADU
(SERBIA, BEOGRAD)**

**HOGSKULEN PA VESTLANDET
(NORUEGA, BERGEN)**

The partnership RESUPERES

The partnership is made up of these 5 European Universities, with different geographical, social, historical, cultural, linguistic, etc. contexts.

The project is based on the strategic choice of the universities, so that each of them contributes its strengths in the areas of resilience work and covers its weaknesses, with the other partners, taking advantage of the experience and the team of professionals of each one of them.

The implementation of the project will take place in 4 phases:

- 1. The development of the transnational meetings (RT),**
- 2. The intellectual outputs (O),**
- 3. The multiplier events (E)**
- 4. Complementary activities (C)**

Results:

What are the expected results of this project?

Benefits related to:

**CLASSROOM, UNIVERSITY, and ACADEMIC
COMMUNITY.**

The expected results will involve the creation of a program for the dissemination of good academic practices, and the creation of new audiovisual tools (websites, apps, multimedia, toolkit) that will increase its resilient capacity.

**THE DREAM IN EXECUTION:
RESUPERES PROJECT-A RESILIENT REALITY**

**Resuperes, nowadays, is the result of intense and very good collective work, a project carried on with unconditional quality, and persevering support from
all:**

RESUPERES TEAM

In European and global society

Individual vulnerability

Life implies the existence of stress and difficulties from which human beings cannot escape. (Rutter, 1990)

To what extent are human beings unable to reverse these vulnerabilities they face in the course of their lives in terms of development?

Risk of vulnerability (and protective factors)

Traumas reactivate the immune and psychological systems of the human being and bring out other psychic damage. Unresilient people reexperience traumatic memories by upsetting their emotional balance.

After a catastrophe, they may experience anxiety, stress, and depression as in the nine eleven attacks.

Resilience helps not only to face adversity but also to benefit from negative impacts.

**Human life is
punctuated by
fragility ...**

**When we speak of
fragility, we refer to a
human condition that
makes us feel
overwhelmed by the
simplest problems and
incapable of internalizing
frustration. In fact, it is a
real instability that grips
all**

**What are the contributions and
the structural elements of
Resilience?
How does this interlink with education?**

Contributions:

- Biology**
- Neural plasticity,**
- Neuroendocrinology,**
- Psychoneuroimmunology**
- Emotion and Emotional Regulation**

Structural Elements of Resilience

- Physiological adaptation
- Psychological Adaptation and Habituation
- Sense of self-efficacy
- Capacity for behavioral self-regulation
- Ability to re-interpret negative experiences or use them as positive learnings

- **All these elements are necessary components for escaping risk routes and being able to cope with adversity.**
- **But no person is invulnerable.**

The five areas of loving relationships

- **Emotional development**
- **Cognitive development**
- **Personality development**
- **Building new interpersonal relationships and emotional ties**
- **Development of psychopathology**

From this optimist approach

The university is impregnated with hope, altruism, creativity, dream, humor, innovation, mastery over the environment, and vitality, and works in the process of training, healthy and happy students, because resilience is more than resisting, is also learning to live.

Another question about Resilience:

**What are the contributions
from psychology
and the neurosciences
to this conceptual field?**

Studies linking resilience to neuroscience are the most recent research approaches.

Among them, the proposal linking resilience with neuroplasticity stands out (Cicchetti and Blender, 2007).

Five points where resilience and neuroscience meet:

- **Plasticity, the world of possibilities**
- **Dreaming, and sleeping to keep growing**
- **The network, our great ally**
- **Novelty, learning to remember**
- **Humor, creating favorable contexts**

Contributions from neuroscientists that directly or indirectly strengthen the educational process

The Neurosciences form a disciplinary body with the contribution of several sciences whose subject of research is the nervous system with particular interest in brain activity and its implication in learning.

- **the brain mechanisms underlying learning, memory, language as a brain faculty, sensory systems, motor systems, attention systems and all the other brain functions that are stimulated day after day in universities;**
- **The teachers to recognize risk factors that may affect brain development processes.**

It bridges the gap between neuroscience research, research into memory systems, and what a teacher does in the classroom.

They can develop companionship, support, empathy, and motivation in students to seek new experiences, to get to know other cultures, and to make friends.

Resilience and institutional leadership behaviours and attitudes

Resilience and leadership ...

El

Leadership can be translated into knowing the strengths and weaknesses of their teachers in the face of adversity, and encouraging them to create, project, and build solutions to problems.

es el caso de mi Tesis.

The predictors of resilience

- (a) Are individual well-being, optimism, and emotional intelligence;
- (b) Resilient individuals cope with stress through direct action strategies, they face problems and try to solve them;
- (c) Social support strengthens resilient relationships

Thus emotional support within the home and positive social exchanges within the university will significantly influence students' ability to cope with threatening situations and emerge stronger.

Finally, I would like to congratulate the Scientific Coordinator of the Resuperes, **Coral Falcó, and her Team,** on the conceptual design of this Congress, in which the factors of promoting resilience are, par excellence, present in all the work of the entire international group that integrates this dream.

I am talking about self-esteem, self-image, self-efficacy, optimism, joy, fun, curiosity, sharing, humor, laughter, cooperation, enthusiasm, creativity, mastery over the environment, and vitality, which are the essence of pleasure and health.

RESUPERES

Intervention proposal for the *Resilience* development in Higher Education. Overcoming Adversity.

Aren't these, in the end, the variables of emotional experience that are the foundation of hope and will allow us to understand, manage and accept the management of stress factors, and as such, to train Resilience with the students and teachers involved in this excellent project?

**Thank you so
much.**

CAROLINA

INVITED LECTURES

RESUPERES

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**CONFERENCE: BUILDING RESILIENCE IN HIGHER
EDUCATION**

Bergen, 25th May 2023

Project RESUPERES

**Dr. Olivera Knežević, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Sport and
Physical Education**

INTERVENTION PROPOSAL FOR THE DEVELOPMENT
OF RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION.
OVERCOMING ADVERSITIES.
RESUPERES

CONTENT:

1. Why was the project requested? What needs does it address?
2. Participating countries
3. Overall objective
4. Specific objectives
5. Implementation (phases)
6. Learning, teaching and training activities
7. Results
8. Conclusion

“Resilience: pain is inevitable, suffering is optional.”
Boris Cyrulnik

1. WHY WAS THE PROJECT REQUESTED? WHAT NEEDS DOES IT ADDRESS?

RESILIENCE

Human capacity to face adversity, to adapt and to overcome tragedies. In other words, adopting a positive attitude. It involves a set of behaviours and ways of thinking that anyone can learn and develop as part of their education, i.e. it can be trained and educable (Robertson & cols., 2015).

Our team considers it is essential to work on Resilience in the educational environment.

AIM TO:

- Provide tools for self-improvement.
- Develop a program to disseminate good practices among university teachers and students.
- Create audiovisual tools that enable online training in Resilience.

2. PARTICIPATING COUNTRIES

- **University of Granada, Spain**
- **University of Algarve (Faro, Portugal)**
- **University Suor Orsola Benincasa (Napoli, Italy)**
- **University of Belgrade (Serbia)**
- **Western Norway University of Applied Sciences (Bergen, Norway)**

3. GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To analyse, design and evaluate an Intervention Program for development of the **constructs of resilience** (coping, self-concept, self-esteem, mindfulness, leadership, etc.)

based on competences within the **areas** that generate resilient behaviour patterns:

- **health** (body expression, inner gymnastics, yoga, physical education and sports),
- **the digital world and communication,**
- **the performing and visual arts and culture,**

These areas are considered a priority in **the development of this construct in Higher Education or university contexts.**

4. SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To identify resilience factors present in the classroom for students and teachers, suitable for resilience development in Higher Education (HE) .

2. To establish European resilience updating and recycling. Sharing of European scenarios.

Characterisation of each department of the university involved in the project, analysis of needs in each country, similarities and divergences.

3. To develop a system for assessing the resilience capacity of students and teaching staff, as a consequence of their evolutionary process, social context and as an effect of the activities proposed from the cultural, artistic, narrative, dramatic, communicative, digital challenges and physical-sports activity and health perspective, which are proposed in this project. To evaluate the reliability, validity and sensitivity of these areas and resilience factors .

4. SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

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4. To design and create a RESUPERES Manual in Higher Education.
5. To create a webpage RESUPERES, as a multilingual interactive platform, for online training.
6. To design, apply and assess an implementation plan of activities such as Soft Skills, Coping Strategies, etc., focused on the improvement of resilient competences, using both internationalisation (5 European universities) and work from different areas (cultural, artistic, virtual, communicative, dramatic and sports activities), as a Pilot Study.
7. To disseminate intellectual outputs (i.e., project results) for the resilience development: digital platform, resilience toolkit, videos, virtual tutorials, etc.

4. SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

8. To create an App RESUPERES, to develop the resilience with autonomy, which serves as a support and methodological resource for Resilience training in Higher Education.
9. To evaluate the global effect of the programme (in the whole educational community), create an itinerary and therefore a subject for the development and improvement of resilience in university educational contexts.
10. To develop and implement a RESUPERES subject in each of the participating universities, and evaluate the implementation of the RESUPERES itinerary in the partner universities.
11. To disseminate all the results provided by the RESUPERES Project, with the aim of establishing a RESUPERES itinerary in Higher Education.

5. IMPLEMENTATION (PHASES)

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I

INITIATION AND PLANNING

PHASE 1. PREPARATION AND START-UP.

- Project Management, Preparation and

Initiation: the Transnational Project

Meeting (TM) 1. (Spain) kick-off meeting

that helped establish the general basis

and agreement for the success of the

project workflow.

PHASE 2. RESUPERES PILOT STUDIES.

- Test phase and gain of experience

through pilot study interventions: aim

to develop the RESUPERES Website

and APP.

- Period of one year. RESUPERES

Workshop-Seminar, to disseminate the

results obtained in this phase.

5. IMPLEMENTATION (PHASES)

2 EXECUTION

PHASE 3. IMPLEMENTATION OF THE subject RESUPERES COURSE

-Objective to plan and start the implementation of the university level course “subject RESUPERES”.

- The outcomes of this course and the 1st International RESUPERES Congress will be obtained as an intellectual project output.

3 EVALUATION AND CLOSURE

PHASE 4. FINAL EVALUATION

- Quality assurance methodology completed and defined.
- Deviation from plans and schedule
- Definition of milestones
- Annual cost of work performed
- CRI (Cost Performance Ratio)
- Deviation from net present value (NPV)
- Deviation from planned break-even time
- Productivity increase
- Fine plan of studies

6. LEARNING, TEACHING AND TRAINING ACTIVITIES

NAME OF THE RESUPERES ACTIVITY	AREA OF INTERVENTION
C2.1. PILOT STUDY SPAIN. IF I FEEL BETTER, I AM BETTER.	Health and physical activity
C2.2. PILOT STUDY PORTUGAL. EMOTIONS AND COMUNICATION!	Audiovisual communication and graphic arts
C2.3. PILOT STUDY SERBIA. I OVMINE! TRAINING IN RESILIENCE.	Sports training
C2.4. PILOT STUDY NORWAY. PROJECT YOUR AVATAR!!	Virtuality, Music, Outdoor activities and Self-Advocacy
C2.5. PILOT STUDY ITALY. DESCRIBING, PROJECTING	Cultural area and narrative literature

6. LEARNING, TEACHING AND TRAINING ACTIVITIES

GENERAL SUMMARY OF PILOT STUDY ACTIVITIES

- **Objectives:** To identify the suitability of the pilot intervention i.e., battery of activities designed to work on the improvement of resilience in students and university teaching staff
- **Procedure:** 5-day interventions will be set up in each of the partner universities.
- **Evaluation:** Pilot studies will be evaluated in the target groups (pre- and post- in students and teachers); implementation process in each country and globally.
- **Strengths:** same academic calendar in all universities, flexible curricula, motivation.
- **Weaknesses:** different curricula.

7. RESUPERES RESULTS

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NAME OF THE RESUPERES RESULT	DESCRIPTION
R1. Manual Resuperes	Background and justification of strategies selected to develop resilience
R2. Webpage RESUPERES	Interactive training platform
R3. App RESUPERES	Mobile app training platform
R4. Subject RESUPERES	University course

7. RESUPERES RESULTS

Diamond Cutting

7. RESUPERES RESULTS

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INTERACTIVE TRAINING PLATFORM & APP RESUPERES

ABOUT

EVALUATION (pre- & post-training
assessment)

MODULES

Structure

Objective

Resilience
Competencies

- Spain: Corporal expression, Physical Preparation
- Portugal: Arts & Creativity (cultural heritage, music...)
- Serbia: Corporal Expression, Breathing exercises
- Norway: Nature activities, Visualization
- Italy: Intercultural communication

8. CONCLUSIONS

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- One of the most ambitious results is the creation and implementation of the **subject RESUPERES i.e., university level course.**
- It will be implemented within participating universities, at different academic degrees to help students develop resilience capacities and competences, such as self-concept, self-esteem, teamwork, leadership.
- Subsequently, the project will be extrapolated to all levels of the educational community at a European and international level.

8. CONCLUSIONS

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8. CONCLUSIONS

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8. CONCLUSIONS

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THANK YOU

RESUPERES

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CONFERENCE: BUILDING RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Bergen, 25th May 2023

Know the Resuperes Manual

Prof. Hugo Mártires

Prof. Marisa Mártires

Co-funded by
the European Union

Resuperes Manual

“There are many challenges that our current educational system must face, one of the main ones being to ease the devastating effects of inequality of educational opportunities, paying special attention to the most vulnerable students, making an inclusive pedagogy a reality that allows educating in resilience and in overcoming and strengthening in the face of adversity.”

(Sousa, in RESUPERES Manual Introduction)

Resuperes Manual

- A brief introduction to the concept of Resilience
- A review on literature on Resilience in Europe (in particular, in partner countries)
- A proposal of activities in several areas of knowledge
- A framework to guide teachers to develop and assess Resilience among students

Resuperes Manual

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1. Theoretical Constructs of Resilience
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 - vi. Protective factors
 - vii. Risk factors
2. The Seven Resilience
3. Resilience in Higher Education in the European Context
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 - vi. Sports

Review

Develop

Evaluate

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Resuperes Manual

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6. Methodology for the development and improvement of resilience
7. Evaluation of the Resilience
8. Final Conclusions
9. References

Resuperes Manual

• Timeline

2022

- Review of best practices, compilation of resilience development and educational materials
- Drafting, review and design of the RESUPERES Manual structure

2024

- Update activities based on the Pilot Studies
- **06** | Integration on Website / App Resuperes
- **12** | Final Version

2023

- **03** | 1st Draft
- **12** | Closing the structure

2025

- **01** | Publication and Dissemination

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Resuperes Manual

- Availability

Document

RESUPERES Website

RESUPERES App

Resuperes Manual

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- Availability

RESUPERES

Modules

Draft

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Bergen, 25th May 2023

Thank you

Grazie Obrigado Takk Gracias Хвала

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RESUPER

Modules

Draft

RESUPERES

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Bergen, 25th May 2023

Thank you

Grazie Obrigado Takk Gracias Хвала

COMUNICATIONS

RESUPERES

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CONFERENCE: BUILDING RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Bergen, 25th May 2023

Resilience in the European Higher
Education Space. Background in Spain.

García Perez, Laura
Padiá Ruz, Rosario
Rojas Cepero, Iago

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Nowadays

A bit of context...

The **transition to university life** entails significant changes that can lead to both **health problems and a decrease in academic performance among students**

(Brewer et al., 2021; Castañeda et al., 2021; Jardim et al., 2021; Tipismana, 2019; Yuste et al., 2021).

Currently, these challenges are further compounded by those brought about by **COVID-19**, which has **resulted in emotional, psychological, and social changes in the academic sphere**

(Hurtubia-Toro et al., 2022; Lozano-Díaz et al., 2020; Save the Children, 2020).

In response to this, both the **OECD (2020)** and the **United Nations (2020)** highlight the **need for resilient education** as a strategy to address all the changes we are facing

(Hurtubia-Toro et al., 2022).

Its also stated that...

A bit of context...

Resilience is one of the factors that predicts a **successful adaptation to the university** environment. (Castañeda et al., 2021).

An **increasing number of studies** are highlighting the need to foster resilience within the **university** setting. (Brewer, 2019; Vizoso, 2019; Lozano-Díaz et al., 2020).

Due to this...

Objectives

We found ourselves in the need to conduct a **literature review focused on studying and analyzing the general characteristics and benefits that resilience work brings to higher education students.**

With the **Objective** of...

Providing an overview of the **current state of the issue and establishing the foundations for designing pilot studies to be carried out** in this European project, specifically in the case of Spain.

Methodology...

For the development of this review...

A **search of the scientific literature** was conducted in the next databases:

Scopus

The Web of Science (WOS)

Methodology...

For the development of this review...

A **search of the scientific literature** was conducted in the next databases:

Scopus

The Web of Science (WOS)

During the
month of
December
2022.

Search
period:
2014 - 2022

Results...

Results...

- Greater growth in scientific publications
- 19 out of the total

We can observe an increase due to the growing interest in resilience.

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Results...

Results...

Results...

Results...

- **Undergraduate** students researches (n=36)
- **Masters** students research: (n=1)

- Most intervened degrees:**
- Education Sciences (n=15)
 - Nursing (n=10)
 - Psychology (n=9)

Results...

In those studies

The instruments used are very diverse, as **resilience is composed of multiple factors**. However, two of the most commonly used instruments are:

The **CD-RIS** (Connor and Davidson, 2003) (n=10).

The **Wagnild and Young Resilience Scale** (1993) (n=7).

**Development of a new resilience scale:
The Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC)**

Kathryn M. Connor, Jonathan R.T. Davidson

OAmg

Results...

In those studies

35 out of 37 (94.6%) reported **positive results in improving** some of the parameters related to **resilience**

Only **2 studies** did not achieve effectiveness in their intervention.

Conclusions...

From all this studies can be concluded that...

- The analyzed studies conclude that **resilience protects against stress and anxiety** in the university context (Gutiérrez-Lozano et al., 2022; Malonda and Módenes, 2018; Morales, 2020; San Román-Mata et al., 2019; Vizoso-Gómez and Arias-Gundín, 2018).
- In the field of physical activity practice, although there are few studies found in the analyzed period, we found a **positive relationship between engaging in physical and sports activities and the ability to overcome adversity** in university students (Bretón et al., 2016; Jeréz and Cabrera-Fernández, 2021; Zurita et al., 2017).

Conclusions...

From all this studies can be concluded that...

- Resilience capacity is an **essential element in the positive adaptation** of university students
(San Román-Mata et al., 2019)
- It is **necessary to work on it** from the university level (Díaz et al., 2020, 2021).
- This need becomes **even more relevant after the pandemic**, with university students who have experienced COVID-19- related confinement currently showing **lower levels of resilience**.
(Romero-González et al., 2021).

With all that, It is concluded that **classroom intervention is effective in reducing stress and improving the resilience of university students.**

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RESUPERES

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CONFERENCE: BUILDING RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Bergen, 25th May 2023

RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION. ASSESSMENT OF INSTRUMENTS

García-Pérez, Laura
Ubago-Jiménez, José Luis
Cepero-González, Mar
Padial-Ruz, Rosario

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- **Introduction**
- **Assesment of instruments**
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RESILIENCE

Is understood as the **capacity of a person** to overcome negative situations and promote the process of overcoming the negative effects that a person faces (Zurita et al. 2017)

RESILIENCE

A **resilient person** is more likely to demonstrate greater flexibility and tolerance to new experiences and easily perform self-regulatory behaviours designed to overcome the adversities they face.

RESILIENCE

Is a **construct** that has been related to multiple variables in the educational field.

Most studied in Spanish publications, associated with resilience, we can find:

RESILIENCE

Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RIS 25)
Connor and Davidson (2003)

Identifies 5 factors: personal competence, high standards and tenacity; trust in intuition, positive acceptance and secure relationships; control; and spiritual influence

VARIABLES AND INSTRUMENTS RELATIONSHIP WITH RESILIENCE

EDUCATIONAL GOALS

Goals Questionnaire for Adolescents (Sanz de Acedo et al. 2003)
GSQ (Goal Setting Questionnaire)

Education contributes to the individual's overall ability to overcome academic challenges and problems that arise in the school context. At a general level, resilience also helps to decrease depression and anxiety and therefore positively influences the academic performance of students (Allan et al. 2014)

VARIABLES AND INSTRUMENTS RELATIONSHIP WITH RESILIENCE

SELF-EFFICACY

Self-efficacy scale by Baessler and Schwarzer (1996)

Self-efficacy and resilience are related because self-efficacy reflects a sense of control over one's environment and an optimistic belief in the face of challenges. Thus, it represents a confident view of the ability to cope with life stressors.

VARIABLES AND INSTRUMENTS RELATIONSHIP WITH RESILIENCE

- Self-concept Form 5 (AF5) (García and Musitu, 2009)

This is a factor that refers to the combination of ideas, feelings, and attitudes that people have about themselves. That is, the labels that a person attributes to themselves as physical, behavioural and emotional indicators and this can directly affect the level of resilience (García-Martínez et al., 2021).

SELF-CONCEPT

VARIABLES AND INSTRUMENTS RELATIONSHIP WITH RESILIENCE

Social skills assesment scale (Goldstein et al. 1980)
Family climate scale (Fernández-Ballesteros and Sierra, 1989)

Social relationships have been shown to enhance resilience. The more social and family support one has, the better adaptations one makes in personal and professional life (Galanis et al. 2022).

**SOCIAL AND
FAMILY
RELATIONSHIPS**

VARIABLES AND INSTRUMENTS RELATIONSHIP WITH RESILIENCE

Cognitive Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (Garnefsky et al. 2001)

There is limited evidence of their relationship, but emotional regulation has historically been repeatedly considered an adaptive strategy for coping with adversity in the face of stressors (Calder, 2021).

**EMOTIONAL
REGULATION**

VARIABLES AND INSTRUMENTS RELATIONSHIP WITH RESILIENCE

Life Orientation Test (Scheier et al. 1994)

Multidimensional Sense of Humour Scale (Thorson and Powell, 1993)

Basic Empathy Scale (Jolliffe and Farrington, 2006)

The relationship between these and resilience is considered essential. This is because they are vitality factors and a negative relationship in them may indicate an inability to cope with the problems of everyday life (Flórez and Sánchez, 2019).

**OPTIMISM
HUMOUR
EMPATHY**

CONCLUSIONS

This research presents the **most common instruments** that can be used **to collect quantitative data related to resilience**. However, further studies are proposed to determine other measurement tools that are useful for the purpose proposed in higher education.

CONCLUSIONS

EDUCATION + RESILIENCE = PERFECT MATCH

*Because if the flapping of a butterfly can cause a tsunami...
Research like ours on resilience can change the educational
world.*

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Bergen, 25th May 2023

RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION. ASSESSMENT OF INSTRUMENTS

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CONFERENCE: BUILDING RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Bergen, 25th May 2023

Assessing Performance Strategies in Athletes: Differences in Practice and Competition Settings

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PERFORMANCE STRATEGIES

- Performance is characterized as an **outcome** of a **high-demand situation** (Howle and Eklund, 2013).
- Performance strategies are psychological techniques used to improve performance in various domains (sports, music, theatre, academics, etc.)

**REGULATE
AROUSAL**

**INFORMATION
PROCESSING**

**EMOTIONAL
CONTROL**

STUDY OVERVIEW:

AIM

To evaluate the differences in performance strategies used by athletes in practice and competition settings.

PARTICIPANTS

120 athletes (62 male and 58 female;
 $M_{age} = 24.83 \pm 4.13$ yrs)

INSTRUMENT

Test of Performance Strategies 2 (TOPS-2)

PERFORMANCE STRATEGIES MEASURED BY TOPS-2:

01

SELF-TALK

Repeating positive self-statements, words or phrases that can motivate you to perform better.

02

AUTOMATICITY

The ability to perform movements automatically without consciously thinking about it.

03

IMAGERY

The ability to visualize a successful performance.

04

ACTIVATION

The ability to intentionally elevate your energy/ mood when you are feeling low.

PERFORMANCE STRATEGIES MEASURED BY TOPS-2:

05

RELAXATION

Effectiveness of physical and psychological relaxation techniques usage.

06

DISTRACTIBILITY

Maintaining the same level of performance regardless of distractions, ex. noise, lack of sleep, bad weather conditions, etc.

07

ATTENTION CONTROL

The ability to control distracting thoughts and shift your focus toward the performance.

08

GOAL-SETTING

The ability to set realistic yet ambitious goals that are related to performance.

RESULTS

Paired samples t-tests were conducted to compare the differences in usage of each performance strategy during practice and competition.

The results revealed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in all performance strategies, except for attention control.

RESULTS

Performance strategy	t statistic	df	p	Mean difference
Self Talk (Competition vs Practice)	-3.603	119	< .001*	-0.617
Emotional Control (Competition vs Practice)	9.067	119	< .001*	-1.992
Automaticity (Competition vs Practice)	-7.187	119	< .001*	-1.425
Goal Setting (Competition vs Practice)	11.084	119	< .001*	2.150
Imagery (Competition vs Practice)	2.548	119	0.012*	0.533
Activation (Competition vs Practice)	8.705	119	< .001*	1.500
Relaxation (Competition vs Practice)	12.500	119	< .001*	2.742
Attention Control (Competition vs Practice)	0.822	119	0.413	0.175

* Significant difference.

RESULTS

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* Significant difference.

WHAT WE CAN CONCLUDE?

- Obvious disparities between performance strategies used in practice and competition setting.
- Better psychological preparation is needed in practice environment in order to improve performance outcomes.
- Coaches and sports psychologists should work with athletes to develop effective strategies that are applicable in both settings.
- TOPS- 2 questionnaire can be used as a valuable tool in this process!

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To get the best results,
performance strategies
need to be **TAUGHT**
and **PRACTICED!**

THANK YOU FOR
YOUR ATTENTION! 😊

Feel free to reach out at
jelena.aleksic@fsfv.bg.ac.rs

Resilience in Outdoor Education

Torbjørn Lundhaug
Associate Professor
RESUPERES BERGEN E+Conference
May 25 2023

**Western Norway
University of
Applied Sciences**

-
- › How do teachers help children building resilience through outdoor education?

Figure 1. Adapted version of Generalised Resistance Resources (GRR) and Sense of Coherence (SOC) (Antonovsky, 1987) combined with Experiential Learning model (Kolb, 2015) used to explore building resilience through outdoor education.

Developing resilience

- › comprehensibility and problem solving
- › support from fellow students and teachers
- › positive view of challenging situations
- › accepting the real-world situations

Experiential learning

- › in demanding and sometimes dangerous situations
- › reflecting on consequences
- › in a friendly learning environment

A resilient life

- › adapt and prepare to improvise in demanding and sometimes dangerous situations.
- › be prepared by learning outdoor basic skills like physical activity in nature, how to dress according to season and weather, harvesting from nature, cooking food on open fire, making a shelter, using basic tools like rope, knife and ax, and navigating with map and compass.

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Thank you so much for your interest and attention!

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CONFERENCE: BUILDING RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Bergen, 25th May 2023

Digital Coping Through Positive Technology

Professor Hugo Mártires

Positive Technology

“The scientific and applied approach that uses the technology for improving the quality of our personal experience with the goal of increasing wellness, and generating strengths and resilience in individuals, organizations, and society.”

(Botella, Riva, Gaggioli, Wiederhold, Alcaniz & Banos, 2012)

“The present and future of positive technologies”

Positive Technology

- The **design and development of technology solutions** that aim to enhance and promote individuals' well-being, happiness, and overall quality of life.
- Focuses on ...
 - ... leveraging digital tools and innovations to foster positive emotions,
 - ... improve mental and physical health,
 - ... facilitate personal growth and flourishing.

The field of positive technology seeks to harness the potential of technology to empower individuals.

Positive Technology

Integration of the scientific principles of well-being into the design of interactive systems.

Positive Technology

Examples

Well-being and mindfulness apps

- guided meditation
- stress reduction techniques
- activities that promote emotional well-being and mindfulness practices

Gamified health and fitness applications

- incorporate game elements, rewards, and social interactions to motivate individuals to engage in physical exercise, healthy habits, and overall well-being

Positive social media platforms

- prioritize fostering positive interactions, supportive communities, and authentic connections
- counteract the negative effects associated with traditional social media

Personal development and goal-setting tools

- features for setting and tracking personal goals, promoting self-reflection, and facilitating behavior change for self-improvement

Literature Review

Mark, G. J., Al-Ani, B., & Semaan, B. (2009). *Resilience through technology adoption: merging the old and the new in Iraq*. In Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on human factors in computing systems

- How technology was adopted and used by citizens to be **Resilient during wartime**.
- Identified properties of resilience:
 - reconfiguring social networks, self-organization, redundancy, proactive practices, and repairing trust in information.
- Conclusions
 - technology supported people in being resilient by enabling them to **control identity**, to **collaborate in travel**, to **create an organizational memory**, and to **provide alternative sources of news and information**.
 - as people adopted and used technology to be resilient, we found a **merging of old and new cultural practices**.

Literature Review

Riva, G., Banos, R. M., Botella, C., Wiederhold, B. K., & Gaggioli, A. (2012). ***Positive technology: using interactive technologies to promote positive functioning***. *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking*, 15(2)

- The impact of new technologies and media on well-being and positive functioning is still somewhat controversial.
- The quality of experience should become the guiding principle in the design and development of new technologies, as well as a primary metric for the evaluation of their applications.
- It is possible to use technology to influence three specific features of our experience
 - Affective quality
 - Engagement/Actualization
 - Connectedness
- ... that serve to promote adaptive behaviors and positive functioning.

Literature Review

FIGURE 18.2 Positive technology levels (Coleman, 1998; Massimini et al., 1996; Fredrickson, 2004; Gaggioli et al., 2013; Helliwell and Putnam, 2004; Nakamura and Csikszentmihalyi, 2001; Riva et al., 2012).

Literature Review

Gill, R., & Donaghue, N. (2016). *Resilience, apps and reluctant individualism: Technologies of self in the neoliberal academy*. In Women's Studies International Forum (54). Pergamon.

- The deep crisis affecting universities
 - large scale institutional and structural transformations produce a psychosocial and somatic catastrophe amongst academics (and other university workers) that manifests in **experiences of chronic stress, anxiety, exhaustion, insomnia and spiraling rates of physical and mental illness**.
- New spaces and services designed with academics in crises at their heart
 - the rolling out of **'well-being' services** within universities of **programs for stress management, mindfulness and Resilience**
 - the **development of new 'apps'** designed for busy or overworked people
 - the rapidly expanding **blogosphere** which has become a key site for **'naming' and sharing such experiences of distress/injury**

Literature Review

Rosenberg, H., Ophir, Y., & Asterhan, C. S. (2018). *A virtual safe zone: Teachers supporting teenage student resilience through social media in times of war*. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 73

- How teacher-student communication through **social network technologies** may **support student Resilience during an ongoing war** (i.e., the 2014 Israel-Gaza war).
- Five content categories of emotional support were identified:
 - I. Caring
 - II. Reassuring
 - III. Emotion sharing
 - IV. Belonging
 - V. Distracting
- The mere existence of continuous **online contact with teachers** also contributed to **Resilience perceptions**.

Literature Review

Shirish, A. (2021). *Positive Technology: A Growing Market With a Potential to Rebuild a Resilient Society During and After the COVID-19 Crisis.*

- The emerging trends in **digital well-being management** by focusing on the mobile health market.
- The use of **positive technology** can positively reverse the automatic route to **mental ill health** that is plausible in the absence of safety perceptions.
- A simple, scalable, and sustainable positive technology design can cater to different user segments
 - policymakers,
 - entrepreneurs,
 - healthcare service providers
- Holistic positive technologies for **fostering societal Resilience.**

Digital Tools for Resilience

[About the toolkit](#) [Using the toolkit](#) [Contribute](#)

Resilience toolkit

Welcome to the AMOSSHE / Unite Students resilience toolkit. This is a resource bank of research, case studies and practical tools to help Student Services professionals in higher education develop student and staff resilience to stress, anxiety and similar barriers to achievement and success.

This toolkit advocates a positive and proactive approach to student resilience, focusing on what higher education providers can do to develop supportive, enabling cultures for students by making improvements to their physical and social environment.

Emotional balance

Use these resources to help students balance their emotional responses to the negative experiences they may encounter academically or socially while studying. Find the resources

here: [Emotional balance resources](#).

Self-management

Use these resources to help students develop self-management techniques for dealing with stress, anxiety and the pressures of higher education. Find the resources here:

[Self-management resources](#).

Social integration / networks / relationships

Use these resources to help students feel integrated, develop their social networks and relationships, and get involved with different networks, communities and extra-curricular

activities. Find the resources here: [Social resources](#).

<https://resiliencetoolkit.org.uk/>

Digital Tools for Resilience

Student Minds® is the student voice on mental health: opening minds, creating understanding and connecting students with resources to thrive. We are an outreach program driven by students and supported by UNSW's Health Promotion Unit.

Student Minds® vision is to improve mental wellbeing and resilience of students in the UNSW community by:

- Reducing stigma surrounding mental health
- Increasing awareness of mental health issues
- Encouraging help-seeking behaviour
- Promoting positive psychological resilience
- Providing opportunities for students to develop personal and professional skills.

Student Minds®

UNSW University of New South Wales
Sydney, Australia

Digital Tools for Resilience

RESILIENCE ASSESSMENT TOOL

"*" indicates required fields

About this Assessment:

The Resilience assessment is a short self-assessment to help you identify your own scores relating to Resilience. It is organized by the four domains of Resilience. This will give you a general sense of where you want to focus your efforts. We encourage you to take this survey as a way to get a snapshot of where you excel and where you may want to focus your energies.

Think about the last year when determining your answer. If you are not sure, select "3" as the survey will not allow you to proceed until you answer each question. The survey should take about 10 minutes to complete.

<https://www.innovativeleadershipinstitute.com/resilience-assessment-tool.html>

Digital Tools for Resilience

RESILIENCE TOOLKIT

Introduction

This resource is an initiative of Glasgow CHP South Sector Youth Health Improvement team developed in partnership with The South Strategic Youth Health and Wellbeing Group. This Emotional Resilience Toolkit provides practical guidance in promoting the resilience of young people as part of an integrated health and wellbeing programme. The resource is designed to be used by workers and volunteers working with young people aged 10 and over.

What do we mean by resilience?

Resilience describes a person's capacity to cope with changes and challenges and to bounce back during difficult times. The more resilient someone is, the better they are at getting through tough times, and the better their chances at recovering from experiences of adversity and trauma (Gilligan 2004)

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Digital Tools for Resilience

Business solutions ▾

Resources ▾

About ▾

Contact Us

MEASURE

Resilience Diagnostic

Measure and map resilience in the workplace.

TRAIN

Precision Training

Futureproof your team with the world's leading program.

SUSTAIN

Rise Digital Toolkit

A comprehensive resilience toolkit, including live expert sessions.

Measure, map and
build resilience at
work

<https://resiliencei.com>

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Digital Tools for Resilience

Metrics you can trust

Scientifically proven. Customized for you.

Powered by the Resilience Diagnostic, discover the strengths and risks across your entire organisation:

- Custom reporting dimensions
- Available in 6 languages
- Duty of care process for individuals at risk
- Comprehensive RD Score report pack
- Ability to benchmark your performance against your sector
- High reliability (Cronbach's Alpha) and Construct Validity
- At the forefront of resilience and wellbeing research

Online Tools for Resilience

A sustainable blended learning experience. Ready when you are.

Equip your team with practical skills to stay calm, energized, positive and focused. This training experience includes

01

02

03

04

05

Full access to the Resilience Digital Toolkit for employees, including the Resilience Diagnostic®, micro-learning content, and advanced personal transformation features

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Digital Tools for Resilience

Categories

Search for anything

Ud

Personal Development > Stress Management > Resilience

How to Develop Emotional Resilience to Manage Stress

Growing Resilience, Mental Toughness and Wellbeing | Thriving Though Adversity | Navigating Challenges | Managing Stress

Bestseller 4.6 ★★★★★ (11,217 ratings) 35,582 students

Created by Robin Hills

Last updated 05/2023 English English [CC], French [Auto], 7 more

Introduction to How to Develop Emotional Resilience to Manage Stress	8 lectures • 29min
Practical Activity: Stress Management - Assess your Ability to Manage Stress	1 lecture • 1min
The Role That Emotions Play In Managing Stress And Developing Resilience	15 lectures • 45min
What is Emotional Resilience?	6 lectures • 13min
The Personal Transition That Everyone Goes Through During Change	14 lectures • 21min
The 3 Competencies of Stress Management	1 lecture • 1min
Competencies of Stress Management - Flexibility	6 lectures • 16min
Practical Activity: Assess your Flexibility	1 lecture • 1min
Competencies of Stress Management - Stress Tolerance	7 lectures • 20min

What you'll learn

- ✓ Identify the ways you manage stress and build your resilience with strategies to develop resilience in yourself and others.
- ✓ Explore why you feel the way that you do in difficult situations and how your emotions impact upon your performance.
- ✓ Examine your experience of emotions to improve well-being and organizational effectiveness.
- ✓ Determine how your emotional intelligence relates to your resilience.

<https://www.udemy.com/course/emotional-resilience/>

A New Frontier ...

- How can AI facilitate tools for Resilience?
- Should we rely on AI to help us coping with stress?
- How Resilient should students become not to be misled by AI?
- ...

Ai

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Thank you

Grazie Obrigado Takk Gracias Хвала

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Bergen, 25th May 2023

RESILIENCE THROUGH ART

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ISTITUTO
SUOR ORSOLA
BENINCASA

UALg
UNIVERSIDADE DO ALGARVE

Western Norway
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Applied Sciences

UNIVERSIDAD
DE GRANADA

University of
Belgrade

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RESILIENCE THROUGH ART

MARTIRES, Marisa | PhD – UALG | ESEC
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How can creativity
and art make us more
resilient?

Drawing: Mariana Gonçalves, age 16 | Title: State of My Soul | Oil Pastels on Paper

*“There’s another way we can **cultivate resilience** that’s often overlooked, which is to **boost our creativity**.”* (Aguilar, 2018)

Drawings: Mariana Gonçalves, age 16 | Title: Resilience | Oil Pastels on Paper

*“Creativity and play **unlock inner resources** for dealing with stress, solving problems, and enjoying life. When we are creative, we are resourceful, and we problem-solve in new and original ways, which fuels our courage. Our thinking expands, and our connection with ourselves and others.”*

(Aguilar, 2018, p.247)

Drawing: Daria Baskirova, age 16 | Title: Ink Splatter | Mixed Media on Paper

Berman points out that

*“The arts enable They also
promote agency and resilience”.*

(2017, p.18)

Metzl, mentions that creative
thinking/production **supports
resilience** in response to adverse
situations.

(2009)

Research based on artistic approaches show that artistic activities promote self-awareness, new perspectives, as well as a sense of action to imagine new possibilities.

(Kaimal, Drescher, Gonzaga, & White, 2014; Kaimal et al., 2016)

Biological studies related to creative self-expression also corroborate this idea.

Hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal axis dysfunction in **stress** response is usually associated with **increased cortisol levels**.

Kaimal, Ray and Muniz, conducted experiments in this context, and obtained results of a **decrease**, in about **75%** of the sample, in the values collected from **cortisol**, in subjects, **after performing artistic activities** (2016).

Creativity produces **increased serotonin levels** in the brain, which in turn triggers increased self-esteem and consequently reduces impulsivity and irritability.

Sylwester cited by Kaplan (2000)

Personal traits that can be **enhanced through art** and are fundamental for resilience:

- Autonomy
- Self-Esteem
- Self-Expression
- Sense of Purpose
- Problem-Solving
- Social Skills

(Developing Resilience Guidebook).

These are skills which help when one faces adversities by enabling the process of emotions and thoughts and resume normal functioning despite difficult situations.

The outcome of art making activities and the procedure of creating, as well as the creative process, can facilitate healing and growth.

(Developing Resilience Guidebook).

Creative individuals tend to be more...

- Autonomous
- Self-Reliant
- Independent
- Assertive
- Self-Accepting
- Resourceful
- Emotionally Sensitive
- Risk Takers

(Malchiodi, 1998).

Their involvement in creative activities helps them attain these qualities, thus enhancing their resilience aptitudes.

(Malchiodi, 1998).

Overview of an art-based activity that illustrates how art can be a powerful tool when it comes to resilience by providing a form of self-expression.

Name of Activity: Fado Emotion Art Activity

Type / Medium: Art Activity / Mixed Media

Activity Description:

Explore the relationship between music and art by reflecting on how music impacts us as well as its intangible quality.

The symbiosis that exists between the two reflects the influence of one medium on the other.

One can express these feelings through color, patterns, shapes, etc...

Activity Description:

Examples that can be used:

- Wassily Kandinsky (Yellow-Red-Blue);
- Piet Mondrian (Boogie Woogie);
- Paul Klee (Polyphony);
- Henri Matisse (Jazz Suite).

Wassily
Kandinsky
(Yellow-
Red-Blue)

Piet Mondrian
(Boogie Woogie)

of Participants: Between 10 / 20

Knowledge Domain: Plastic Arts

Duration: 120min.

Resources/Materials:

Fado music, water colour paper/white Canson paper, Indian ink, paintbrushes, colour pencils, markers, water colours, magazines, scissors, glue, etc.

Facilities:

Large room with drawing tables and natural light.

Skills for the development and improvement of Resilience:

Memory triggers, mood altering, emotional unlock, source of comfort and inspiration, foster creativity.

Development:

Start with a brief outline of the activity to be developed and show various artworks created by well-known artists as examples that will serve as a reference.

Explain that both art and music hold the ability to evoke an emotional response in us, and that together they can trigger memories, alter our mood, or even unlock emotions. They can also be used as a source of comfort and inspiration.

Example:

Whilst listening to Portuguese Fado, students and teachers had the opportunity to reflect upon the music that they heard and thought about how it made them feel.

They expressed their emotions using colours, patterns, shapes, etc.

They could express a mood, a memory or even express how the music inspired them.

At the end of the activity, students wrote a descriptive memory text about the task they performed and reflect on the result/outcome of their artmaking.

Listening to Fado I felt an unbearable rush of emotions, both good and bad but in a way too much for one person to handle alone. This experience was reminiscent of the ocean, my sanctuary when I feel lonely. The sea, much like the waves, is an unstoppable force and always welcomes my emotional turmoil and replenishes me with peace and hope.

Advantages:

Different music can bring on different outcomes and can be chosen to tailor different needs.

This activity is also beneficial because no specific art skills are required to be able to obtain a satisfying result, as is the case of the art medium/technique to be applied.

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Art Therapy Guidebook – Developing Resilience: Recuperado de <https://arttherapyresources.com.au/shop/developing-resilience/>

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RESILIENCE THROUGH ART

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THANK YOU!

Drawings: Mariana Gonçalves, age 16 | Title: Resilience | Oil Pastels on Paper

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Bergen, 25th May 2023

Sport can bring rival communities together

**Marina Maletic, Jelena Aleksic, Ana Ristevski, Dimitrije
Pavlovic**
Faculty of Sport and Physical Education

Summary:

- **Introduction**
- **What is the purpose of sport?**
- **Rivalry in sport**
- **Unity through sport**
- **Examples**
- **Conclusions**

Purpose of sport?

- **agression?**
- **war fights?**
- **historical records: Gladiators, Pankration...**

Division and rivalry in sport?

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- **rivalry: essential part of sports competitions**

GROUP
BELONGING

MUTUAL
PURPOSE /
GOAL

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**“Sport has the power to unite people
in a way little else does.”**

Nelson Mandela

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A bridge to overcome difference!

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the European Union

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True sportsmanship rises above

- **RACISM**
- **OPRESSION**
- **DISCRIMINATION**
- **DIVISION**

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SPORT BRINGS THE WORLD TOGETHER!

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CONFERENCE: BUILDING RESILIENCE IN HIGHER
EDUCATION

Bergen, 25th May 2023

GROUP COHESION DYNAMICS

Atencia Rodríguez, María Elena
Ortiz Delgado, Candela
Alonso Vargas, José Manuel
Collado Fernández, Diego

INTRODUCTION

Definition of group techniques

“How community members relate to each other, what roles they play and how well they cooperate, is an important element that improves resilience”

Dörnyei y Murphey (2003)

INTRODUCTION

Group techniques into the sport field

Two group factors have generally been regarded as important for individuals to adhere to physical exercise, that is, **group cohesion** and **social support** (Christensen, 2006).

Group cohesion in sport has been defined as “a dynamic process which is reflected in the tendency of a group to stick together and remain united in the pursuit of its instrumental and objectives and / or for the satisfaction of member affective needs” (Carron, 1982; Carron, Brawley, & Widmeyer, 1998).

GROUP COHESION DYNAMICS

Duration: 1.30H

N° of activities: 12

N° of participants: 20

Objectives:

1. To enable a high degree of social relations between teachers and students from different countries within the Resuperes group.
2. To ensure the cohesion of the international Resuperes group through socialization and cooperation activities.

Methodology: Socialising, Collaborative

Installation: Body Expression Room

Material: Balls, stickers, 3 skeins of wool, 10 masks

Constructs to be developed for the improvement of PS RESUPERES Resilience:

Constructs of the Pilot Study:

- Social competence.
- Problem solving (Coping).
- Sense of purpose and future.
- Autonomy and personal ideology
(Heritage: Heritage and cultural heritage).

Other constructs to develop:

- Self-concept and self-esteem.
- Creativity and optimism.
- Introspection.
- Initiative.
- Sense of humour.
- Teamwork.
- Leadership and self-efficacy.

ACTIVITY 1. “TAKE CHARGE!”

Development - Participants will be grouped as quickly as possible according to the following statements:

They are from the same country

They want to travel to the same continent

That they like the countryside, the village or the city

That they were born in the same decade

That they have the same number of siblings

MORE STATEMENTS

That they like the same individual sport

That they like the same adventure sport

Like the same team sport

That they like the sun, rain or snow

That they like the beach or the mountains
(countryside)

ACTIVITY 2. “WE ORDER OURSELVES”

Development: All participants will stand in a single line on a line drawn on the floor in the following order:

By height, from shortest to tallest

Eye colour, from lightest to darkest

By the distance from its
population to Granada

Hair colour, from lightest to darkest

By age, from youngest to oldest

CONCLUSION

Group dynamics based on cooperation are effective for:

- ❖ Improving personal knowledge and knowledge of the group members.
- ❖ Determining strengths and weaknesses.
- ❖ Strengthening the group relationship.
- ❖ Facilitating cohesion of heterogeneous groups.

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The Tale of the Self between Movement, Writing and Art. Strategies for resilience education'

Stefania Maddalena - Federica Paolozzi - Martina Ercolano - Roberta Petrecca

GOALS:

- Humanisation of work
- Built resilience in university contexts through narration

INTRODUCTION

The changes, the continuous reorganisations, mergers and divisions of the various teaching and administrative structures that have taken place in recent years in the university system, the introduction of fixed-term contracts, the difficulties in finding funding, competition with colleagues, and the precariousness of one's job position have led academic staff to be much more exposed to risks such as work-related stress (SLC) and burnout. (Ingusci et al., 2019). The development of research in both work psychology and organisational resilience studies shows that there are 'intangible' factors that escape the normal rationalisation of work and organisation and these are social support (Karasek and Theorell 1990) the role of the individual in modifying the impact of work demands and resources on motivation and energy in the form of personal resources (Bakker & Demerouti, 2016) such as confidence in one's abilities and optimism about one's future (Xanthopoulou, Bakker, et al., 2007). Resilience in organisations is not only its ability to adapt to external circumstances but means renewal, transformation and dynamic creativity from within (Lengnick-Hall, et al., 2011). It is therefore considered desirable for universities to promote training interventions that are oriented not only towards learning new professional knowledge and skills, but also towards enhancing personal resources such as self-efficacy, optimism and resilience, which are fundamental for preventing the risk of work-related stress. "The contribution of training is intended to help the person to dwell reflexively in the work context, to learn to think, to experience the pleasure of thinking, to adopt a new outlook through which to look at oneself, to think oneself to change oneself in particular through self-narration in order to become thoughtfully present subjectivity with respect to the many and varied professional events, to acquire awareness of who one is, of why one thinks in a certain way, why one does, why one acts in a certain way beyond the role one holds, to acquire knowledge of one's experiences of awareness, of one's relational modalities, of one's mental functioning mechanisms" (Rossi, 2012).

Model developed on the basis of the 'Casita' of resilience (BICE 1996)

High percentage of students who drop out of higher education before graduation is considered a critical factor in the Italian university system (CNVSU 2011; Di Pietro 2006; Cingano and Cipollone 2007, ANVUR 2013) The average university drop-out rate within the first year of study is equivalent to 1 out of 10 students. (Tinto, 1988; Valto & Nuora, 2019) A growing phenomenon is the number of suicide of university students (ISTAT). On the basis of these initial findings and the broader evidence reported in the literature, a greater focus on students' cognitive-motivational factors would guarantee a reduction in the risk of dropping out (Pintrich, 1999, 2004; Diseth & Kobbeltvedt, 2010; Heikkila et al., 2011). Certain studies in specific have demonstrated that resilience-building pathways in the university context could effectively protect students from experiencing negative stress and excessive academic pressure. These programmes would ensure the maintenance of high levels of performance, motivation, and resilience in the face of unfavourable academic conditions. (Romano et al., 2021) At the same time, it is necessary to clarify that resilience characteristics derive from the interaction between multiple personal variables and contextual factors. (De La Fuente et al., 2017)

METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK EPISTEMOLOGICAL APPROACH

The «narrative thought», defined by the scientist J. Bruner, represents the «natural aptitude of human beings to organise experience in narrative form». Through pedagogy, the autobiographical-narrative method has the possibility of observing the individual living the crisis of his time, helping him to overcome it by interpreting and re-elaborating himself and his experiences, giving them a meaning in a projectual and therefore formative perspective. Autobiography, therefore, is a research tool and a methodology capable of orienting to reinforce useful lines of action in the educational sphere.

Adapted by: M.H. Immordino-Yang (2017), Affective Neuroscience and Education

Moreover, it is possible to identify the autobiographical-narrative approach as a pedagogical device that can offer teachers and future teachers' spaces for training and authentic self-education. Above all, it is important that teachers first develop their own resilience in order to become resilience mentors. This is a fairly recent area of research that has enabled us to understand it as a dynamic process in which risk and projective factors interact and interface in relation to the environment in which one lives and works.

- But what exactly does teacher resilience consist of?
- Why should teachers develop it beyond their role as mentors and educators?
- What strategies can they use in their daily work at school?

CULTURAL HERITAGE

From the perspective of promoting resilience in organisational contexts, cultural heritage is identified as a tool for the development of the now necessary autobiographical competence. The museum as a space of non-formal education lends itself to the construction of cultural mediation paths in which the subject/visitor, supported and urged on by an educator, is engaged in a process of reflection and progressive unveiling of the meaning associated with the cultural object: a meaning that is not merely transmitted, but discovered by the visitor starting from an autonomous and authentic understanding, i.e. an interpretation of the work of art that passes through the subject's own experience. Starting from a constructivist approach, supplemented by a transactional perspective that values transactive interaction with the environment, we look at learning in depth (cognitive, emotional, relational). That meaning is then shared, narrated, becoming a common heritage of ideas. Dewey in 'Art as Experience' (1951) emphasises the close link between art and life, highlighting the importance of reconstructing the continuity between works of art and everyday facts, actions and passions. In the words of Umberto Eco, we talk about open Opera (1962): the spectator is a constitutive and indispensable element of the artistic phenomenon.

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RESUPERES

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CONFERENCE: BUILDING RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Bergen, 25th May 2023

The importance of breathing exercises for physical and mental health

Ana Ristovski

Faculty of Sport and Physical Education

UNIVERSIDAD
DE GRANADA

University of
Belgrade

Content

- Introduction
- Breathing pattern disorder
- Ideal breathing patterns
- Breathing exercises: **crocodile breathing, box breathing, Buteyko breathing technique, Wim Hof breathing technique**
- The benefits of breathing exercises and their effects on the physical and mental health

Introduction

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- Breathing: one of the most important functions of our body
- Breathing is the only process that we can do consciously or completely unconsciously

The aim is to enhance awareness of the importance of breathing exercises and to emphasize their benefits!

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the European Union

Breathing pattern disorder

Biochemical

Biomechanical

Psychological

Ideal breathing patterns

Co-funded by
the European Union

Normal

Diaphragmatic
breathing

Abnormal

Chest breathing

**Nose breathing is healthy
brathing!**

**NOSE
BREATHING**

**MOUTH
BREATHING**

**A normal breathing pattern
at rest will be nose and
abdominal breathing!**

Breathing exercises

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01 Crocodile Breathing

This exercise or technique is used to teach and train diaphragmatic breathing

02 Box Breathing

Box breathing is a breathing exercise to assist patients with stress management

Breathing exercises

Co-funded by
the European Union

03 Buteyko Breathing Technique

Natural way to
improve health

increase energy and
concentration

reduce stress and
anxiety levels

improve sleep
quality

04 Wim Hof breathing technique

The exercises are focused on deep and rhythmic inhalations and exhalations, described by Wim as 'controlled hyperventilation or power breathing'

The benefits of breathing exercises

Co-funded by
the European Union

- Breathing becomes **more efficient**
- Better **lung health**
- It improves your **core muscle stability**
- It helps **lower your blood pressure**
- A healthy **cardiovascular system**
- Optimum levels of **carbon dioxide** in the arterial blood
- Mental calmness and **resilience**
- **Stress reduction**

RESUPERES

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CONFERENCE: BUILDING RESILIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Bergen, 25th May 2023

Thank you for your attention!

ISTITUTO
SUOR ORSOLA
BENINCASA

Western Norway
University of
Applied Sciences

UNIVERSIDAD
DE GRANADA

University of
Belgrade

Resilience and Music: State-of-the-Art and Research Agenda

David G. Hebert, PhD

Professor, Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Bergen

Honorary Professor, Education University of Hong Kong

Affiliated Professor, University of the Faroe Islands

RESUPERES Project Multiplier Event

Thursday 25 May 2023

HVL-Kronstad campus, Bergen

**Resilience and Music:
State of the Art and Research Agenda**

STATUS OF CURRENT KNOWLEDGE

Reflections from the most famous scientist of the 20th century ...

“I KNOW THAT THE MOST
JOY IN MY LIFE HAS COME
TO ME FROM MY VIOLIN.”

- ALBERT EINSTEIN

CLASSIC *f*M

Cognitive and Social Skills: *Knowledge* in Music Education

Specific Types:

- Propositional/descriptive knowledge: facts to be learned/memorized.
- Procedural knowledge: How to do something.
- Metaknowledge: knowledge about knowledge (taxonomies, complex relationships).
- Tacit/situational knowledge: unwritten rules, common sense, emotional intelligence, taken for granted.
- Encoded knowledge: data, symbols, language, notation
- Empirical knowledge: gained through senses (main type of posteriori knowledge)
- Dispersed/distributed knowledge (e.g. opera)

Research Findings: *Resilience* and Music (I)

- “awareness of the **sources of resilience** and a family systems perspective can inform music therapy clinicians.” -Pasiali, V. (2012). Resilience, music therapy, and human adaptation: nurturing young children and families, *Nordic Journal of Music Therapy*, 21:1, 36-56, DOI: 10.1080/08098131.2011.571276
- “in line with current thinking in social theory, I offer some cautions regarding the **over-reliance on standard approaches to resilience at the expense of more creative and productive strategies** for managing adversity and trauma” - Holmes, P. (2017). Towards a conceptual framework for resilience research in music training and performance: A crossdiscipline review. *Music Performance Research*, 8, 114-132.
- [This] “qualitative study involving a thematic content analysis of in-depth interviews seeks to investigate the contributing factors to resilience: the personality, situational and social factors that are most effective in supporting and increasing **resilience within a sample of professional musicians.**” - O’Donnell, H. (2020). *Investigating the contributing factors to resilience in coping with adversity: A qualitative exploratory study of professional musicians in the context of COVID-19.* SRH Fernhochschule.
- “...the findings from this study have important implications for the **power of sustainable, integrated and community-focused approaches for fostering psychological well-being and community health.**” - Gerber, M. M., Hogan, L. R., Maxwell, K., Callahan, J. L., Ruggero, C. J., & Sundberg, T. (2014). Children after war: A novel approach to promoting resilience through music. *Traumatology: An International Journal*, 20(2), 112.

Research Findings: *Resilience* and Music (II)

“Music can enhance the creative resilience of individuals, communities and organizations. Shared musical experiences are powerful channels of identity formation or disidentification. Collective musical practices nurture values that can be helpful when integrated within **sustainability-oriented worldviews**: cooperation, listening and tuning in to each other, and sharing responsibilities towards common desires. Music as a complex social and aesthetic system can stimulate an aesthetics of complexity, encouraging **openness to the ambiguities, ambivalences, contradictions and creatively chaotic dimensions of reality**, rather than levelling them into a coherent logical system.”

Kagan, S., & Kirchberg, V. (2016). Music and sustainability: organizational cultures towards creative resilience—a review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 135, 1487-1502.

Research Findings: *Resilience* and Music (III)

“In terms of **musical activity that builds a capacity for resilience**, I argue that this notion of ecological public services has the potential to account for outcomes within which music has played an often-invisible part. (...) publicly funded music projects, some of which aim to build resilience, share common features aligned with an ecological view of reform in health, education and social work systems” (p.5)

“If this reform agenda becomes a reality and public services of the 21st century start allocating more resources from a “needs and outcomes” perspective, and less via the visible institutions such as hospitals and schools, then socio-musical activity that builds the capacity for resilience has a bright future.” (p.12)

Brader, A. (Ed.). (2011). *Songs of resilience*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing.

Research Findings: *Resilience* and Music (IV)

“Instead of an education that promotes preoccupation with profit-margins, what protection of both the environment and cultural heritage requires is a larger proportion of students committed to **questioning assumptions and actively promoting ways to transform society**—to improve human rights, promote social justice, protect the environment, and support artistic and cultural expression. ” (p.180)

Hebert, D. G. (2022). Nature Conservation and Music Sustainability: Fields with Shared Concerns. *Canadian Journal of Environmental Education*, 25, 175-189.

“Perhaps no recent development more vividly demonstrates the powerful relationship between music and political thought as the ongoing war in Ukraine, which has served as the backdrop for an array of videos disseminated via social media that depict **music performances in wartime** contexts. (...) According to the accompanying explanation, ‘A Ukrainian pianist has been filmed playing a final rendition of Chopin in the ruins of her house after it was badly damaged by Russian shelling. (...) Other viral videos have shown, for instance, a young Ukrainian violinist playing music from a Kiev bomb shelter (Forces News, 2022) and a Ukrainian refugee girl singing”

Hebert, D. G. & Johnson, D. (forthcoming, 2024). Global music communities and civic engagement in the digital age. In D. Blandy & F. Bastos (Eds.), Promoting Civic Engagement Through Art Education: A Call to Action for Creative Educators. Routledge.

What makes the arts uniquely important today?

- Development of cognitive and social skills: *concentration, cooperation, self-awareness, emotional control, aesthetic judgment, self-discipline, curiosity and creativity.*
- Meaning-making that transcends mundane consumerism
- Community health and wellbeing through enhanced cooperation
- Intergenerational social cohesion through appreciation of history and cultural heritage
- Conflict resolution: peace and cultural diplomacy

**Resilience and Music:
State of the Art and Research Agenda**

NEW DEVELOPMENTS & ONGOING DEBATES

Rediscovering Resilience of Arts in a Fragile World:

What likely lies in the future of the arts?

- Instant global cooperation, recognition and distribution via Internet
- Mass commodification vs. efforts to protect heritage from exploitation
- Artificial Intelligence (AI) integrated with human input
- Augmented Reality (AR) applications that extend arts experience
- Virtual Reality (VR) environments for experience of arts

Popular VR Headsets: Oculus and Pico

Popular VR Music Apps

The screenshot displays the SideQuest website interface, which is a platform for downloading VR applications. At the top, there is a search bar with the text "Search games..." and a magnifying glass icon. To the right of the search bar are links for "SIGN IN" and "SIGN UP". Below the search bar is a navigation menu with the following items: "HOME", "GAMES", "SUPPORT", "PROMOTE", "GET SIDEQUEST", and "GIVEAWAYS". The main content area is a grid of 12 app cards, each featuring a cover image, the app name, a rating (represented by a star and a number), and icons for heart, download, and star. The apps shown are:

- VRtuos**: Rating 4.08 (8), FREE.
- GrooVR - Air dru...**: Rating 4.19 (9), PAID.
- Enhance VR - Ne...**: Rating 4.45 (5), FREE.
- ZenVR**: Rating 4.24 (3), PAID.
- 3D Organon VR A...**: Rating 3.67 (2), FREE.
- Grand Reality : VR...**: Rating 4.03 (3), FREE.
- Maestro: The Masterclass**: Rating 4.38 (8), FREE. Description: "Step on the podium and become a true orchestra conductor in Maestro: The Masterclass. Play hands free or grab a chopstick and master the real hands motions that command the orchestra through an off the rail conducting masterclass that culminates with an epic symphonic concert in a packed opera house..."
- Human Anatomy VR**: Rating 4.72 (2), FREE.
- VIRTUALSPEECH**: Rating 3.82 (1), FREE.
- LANGUAGE LAB**: Rating 4.82 (1), FREE.
- Dino**: Rating 3.77 (1), FREE.

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VR opportunities in HVL Medielab

AR Musical Spaces: Sydney Opera House Example

Augmented Reality: Ukelele Example

Augmented Reality: Bass Guitar Example

VR Conducting: “Maestro” App

VR Drumming App

But VR can be dangerous...?

**Resilience and Music:
State of the Art and Research Agenda**

RELEVANT PROJECTS AT HVL-BERGEN

Celebrating a New Book

Odd Torleiv Furnes

DYBDELÆRING I MUSIKK

Musikalsk forståelse gjennom
sansning, følelser og begreper

Deep Learning in Music

By: Odd Torleiv Furnes

HVL Associate Professor

Giving workshop for RESUPERES on Friday

The book (in Norwegian language) shows how learning of music contributes to holistic cognitive development.

Celebrating a New Book

Features of the Book:

- Promotes intercultural understanding and rethinking of educational foundations, which contribute broadly to ***resilience***
- Expands the philosophy of education to include ideas of major non-western educational thinkers
- Analyzes non-western concepts critically and considers their relevance to schools worldwide
- Rethinks approaches to education in arts and humanities through decolonized philosophy of education

Research Background: Global studies, comparative education, musicology

CULTURAL DIPLOMACY & RESILIENCE

Partners in Global Competence (Hong Kong/Bergen) Doctoral Partnership

Hong Kong Strengths

- Cosmopolitan harbour city, with 7.5 million people, a major global financial center
- Access to China, world's largest economy, but in an English-language program
- Highly-ranked university with global profile in the field of Education
- Professors who are widely published scholars and leaders of professional organizations
- Professors from China and Japan with experience in western nations (degrees from US, UK, etc.)

Bergen Strengths

- Access to major cultural center and one of Europe's strongest economies
- Rapidly developing professions-oriented university with growing research profile
- Studies in contemporary European *Bildung* educational theory and university pedagogy
- Widely published and cited professors with extensive experience in doctoral supervision
- Professors who have deep familiarity with China and other countries

Global Competence Partnership Course Development

New Doctoral and Postgraduate Courses

- The next generation of college and university professors will need **not only theoretical knowledge but also a high level of practical skills informed by intercultural experience**. The Global Competence Partnership (GCP) will actively develop several innovative courses in an intensive COIL (collaborative online international learning) format to strengthen doctoral studies and faculty professional development.

Examples of course titles under development [1 ECTS, PhD-level, also for faculty professional development]:

- Foundations and Practices of University Pedagogy, Assessment and Evaluation: Feedback Literacy, Methods for Effective Online Higher Education, Doctoral Supervision, Diversity and Inclusion in Higher Education, Research Methods in Higher Education, Reflective Methods for Researching One's Own Practice, R&D Project Management in Higher Education, Research Dissemination: Effective Publications and Presentations ...

CABUTE

Uganda Project Objectives

1. To strengthen the quality and relevance of postgraduate (Master- and PhD-level) teacher education and research programs and methods in selected subjects.
2. To strengthen postgraduate (Master and PhD-level) teacher educator education and research systems in the selected subjects.
3. To increase competence and capacity of higher education faculty and teacher educators.
4. To improve institutional small-scale infrastructure and equipment for education and research.
5. To improve gender equality and inclusion of marginalized groups in teacher education and research in selected subjects.
6. To increase availability of opportunities for lifelong learning among teacher educators.
7. To increase engagement with the Ugandan Ministry of Education and Sports and other relevant stakeholders for dissemination of knowledge.

MUSIC TALKS Concept:

Strengthening resilience through developing research-based methods for use of music to promote social cohesion and civic engagement.

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Western Norway
University of
Applied Sciences

Concept

Consists of 13 methods to help non-formal education youth workers lead:

- Music listening activities
- Music appreciation activities
- Music discussions

These activities are aimed to develop young people's ability to:

- Formulate personal attitudes
- Explore their identity
- Develop critical thinking and communication skills
- Cultivate cooperation

Methodology Activity Types

Energizers

- Activities to help participants stay active (physically move, sing songs, interact with each other)

Team building

- Activities to help participants get to know each other better, create a sense of community, and a united team

Finding common ground

- Activities to help participants come to a similar understanding about a topic, opinion, interests, achievable goals or objectives

Evaluation / Debriefing

- Activities after each method to provide information and feedback about the joint work, learning process and environment, achievement of goals, feelings of participants, etc. [**7:30**]

MT Methodology Manual

All methods follow a standardized format:

- Method summary
- Function
- Objectives
- Resources / Preparation
- Step-by-step description of how to conduct the activity / online adaptation (*where applicable*)
- Questions for debriefing
- Tips for the facilitator
- Research support

<https://sites.google.com/view/music-talks-erasmus-project/about-us>

ANTHEM

10-20 min.

face-to-face

10-20

Summary	A musical team building exercise where participants share music they love and find musical common ground within the group.
Function	Team building Triggering creativity Raising awareness Finding common ground
Objectives	Develop group identity and cohesion Engender group discussion of music appreciation Boost communication, presentation and argumentation skills Develop awareness of the role of lyrics, melodies and other elements in music perception Promote tolerance and understanding of diversity among young people (bullying, mobbing)
Resources /preparation	Smartphones
Step-by-step description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ask participants to sit in a circle and choose one song that they think would characterise or represent their group the best. 2. Divide participants into pairs and ask them to share the musical piece with their teammate and explain why this song would be the right one for the whole group. Ask them to play it. 3. Ask participant pairs to decide on one from the two songs that will work for both of them. 4. Combine pairs to make small groups of four participants and ask pairs to share the chosen song from each pair. 5. Discuss and agree on one song that will work for all four of them. 6. Repeat combining groups until all participants meet. 7. The final chosen song should represent the whole group and can be the trigger song for gathering, attention or simply the anthem of the event. 8. Do debriefing, reflect on the results.

Rediscovering Resilience of Arts in a Fragile World:

Expanding the Interdisciplinary Research Agenda

- Sustainability: nature and culture, education beyond schools
- Socio-technological change: Challenges of AI, VR, etc.
- Intercultural and international relations: Conflict resolution for peace and cultural diplomacy

END

Resilience and Music: State-of-the-Art and Research Agenda

David G. Hebert, PhD

Professor, Western Norway University of Applied Sciences, Bergen

Honorary Professor, Education University of Hong Kong

Affiliated Professor, University of the Faroe Islands

RESUPERES Project Multiplier Event

Thursday 25 May 2023
HVL-Kronstad campus, Bergen

“Resilience, Emotion and Communication” University of Algarve

University of Education and Communication
FARO March 12th to 17th 2023

Students:
Helena Monteiro
Miriam Graça

Co-funded by
the European Union

RESUPERES
Resilience
in Higher
Education

Contents Of This Template

1. About Faro, Algarve
2. The week:
 - 13 March – Monday
 - 14 March – Tuesday
 - 15 March – Wednesday
 - 16 March – Thursday
 - 17 March – Friday
3. The importance of this project
4. Beautiful memories

01 FARO

FARO IS A MIX OF

Historic Sites

Natural Beauty

02

**The development
of the week**

13 March – Monday

- Conference: “Resilience, Emotion and Communication”, with Teacher Carolina de Sousa.

- Coffee Break.

- Introduction to activity C2.5 “Resilience, Emotion and Communication”, Pilot Study of the RESUPERES European Project in Portugal.

- Lunch at the University restaurant of Penha Campus.

- Workshop “Photo opportunity - Introduction”.

14 March – Tuesday

- Historical heritage of the city of Faro: discovering the old town and the Municipal Museum of Faro.
- Lunch at the University restaurant of Penha Campus.
- Faro city historical heritage: discovering Modernism.

15 March – Wednesday

TAVIRA

“Discovering the city of Tavira: cultural heritage, Fado and photography”:

- Ascent to the old Castle and observation of the urban fabric of the city and its Development.
- “Colors” photography exhibition by Fernando Ricardo, Museum Palácio da Galeria.
- History, culture, and heritage: 120 years of photography. Museum of Photography.
 - “Photo opportunity practice in urban space I”.

Practice of “Photo opportunity II, in urban space”

FADO

“Fado with History”: Concert and Workshop by Fado com História Association in Igreja da Misericórdia (Church of Mercy).

Practice of “Photo opportunity III, in urban space: From Church of Mercy to Church of Carmo”, a look at the expressions of balance and emotions in architecture

16 March – Thursday

- Workshop of photography: fundamentals of photography and digital image processing.
- Lunch at the University restaurant of Penha Campus.
- Arts workshop in music and visual arts: “Fado Emotion Arts Activity”.
Singer: Viviane, accompanied by Portuguese guitar and acoustic viola.
- Conclusion of arts workshop in music and visual arts: “Fado Emotion Arts Activity”.
- Resuperes dinner.

RESUPERES dinner

Restaurant at the top floor of Hotel Eva,
with the presence of Versus Tuna (a group
of traditional academic music)

17 March – Friday

The City Of Lisbon

Visit to the Fado Museum in Lisbon and conference by musicologist Rui Nery: Coordinator of the candidature of Fado to the immaterial cultural heritage of humanity by UNESCO.

Conference topic: Fado as a factor of social and cultural resilience.

03 The importance of this project

RESUPERES is a project - integrated in education - a process that occurs throughout the entire life cycle and serves multiple dimensions, that is, it does not focus only on purely academic content, but also includes social skills, emotions, self-esteem, motivation, cultural competences, communication skills, and others.

04 Beautiful Memories

Thank you!

POSTERS

PRE-PROJECT RESUPERES. SPECIFIC CRITERIA TO BE MEASURED IN THE FIRST PILOT STUDY (RESILIENCE AND PSYCHOSOCIAL CONSTRUCTORS)

García-Pérez, Laura; Rojas Cepero, Iago; Ubago-Jiménez, José Luis y Padiá-Ruz, Rosario

INTRODUCTION

The university population has been the subject of study over the years, as it is a transitional period in which numerous changes occur biologically, as well as psychologically, emotionally, sexually, and socially. These changes directly affect the physical and mental health of university students. During the university period, it is essential to **consolidate healthy habits** and **prevent disruptive behaviours** that affect students' health, and **RESILIENCE** is a vehicles for this (San Román-Mata et al., 2019).

Resilience is the ability of humans to cope with adversity, to adapt and overcome challenges, trauma, threats, or severe stress, so a resilient person is more likely to demonstrate greater flexibility and tolerance to new experiences and easily perform self-regulatory behaviours designed to overcome the adversities they face (Chaharbaghi et al., 2022).

The development of resilience may be related to other psychosocial factors such as **self-esteem** (Gacek et al. 2022), **mental health conditions** (Stanton et al., 2020), and **personality development** (Fernandez-Bustos et al., 2019), among others.

METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

The **aim** of this study was to determine which instruments could be used throughout the project to quantitatively measure the resulting effects.

To achieve this objective, a literature search was conducted on which validated instruments were optimal for inclusion in the project.

These were the main findings:

ASPECT TO WORK ON		MEASUREMENT TOOL	REFERENCE	
RESILIENCE AND ITS COMPONENTS	Resilience	CD-RISC 25	Connor y Davidson (2003)	
	Social competence	Social skills	Social skills assessment scale	
	Troubleshooting	Coping	Coping Strategies Inventory	
	Sense of purpose and future	Educational goals	Reduced Goals Questionnaire Adolescents (CMA-R)	López-Mora et al. (2017)
			Goals Questionnaire for Adolescents (CMA)	Sanz de Acedo Lizarraga et al. (2003)
	Cultural heritage and inheritance	Personal ideology		
Autonomy				
OTHER ISSUES TO WORK ON	Physical activity	IPAQ-SF	Craig et al. (2003)	
	Self-concept: academic, social, emotional, family and physical	AF-5	García y Musitu (2001)	
	Self-esteem	Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSE)	Rosenberg (1965)	
	Depression, Anxiety and Stress	DASS-21	Lovinbond y Lovinbond (1995)	
	Personality factors	BIG FIVE-44	Benet-Martinez y John (1998)	
	Empathy	Brief Basic Empathy Scale	Jolliffe y Farrington (2006)	
	Emotional Regulation	Cognitive Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (CERQ)	Garnefski et al. (2001)	
	Self-efficacy	Self-efficacy scale	Baessler y Schwarzer (1996)	
	Optimism	Life Orientation Test Questionnaire	Scheier et al. 1994	
	Humour	Multidimensional Sense of Humour Scale	Thorsol y Powell (1991)	

MAIN CONCLUSIONS

Of all the instruments analysed , the following were selected for the project. First, **CD-RISC 25** was used to measure resilience, as it has been used in different research studies of high scientific rigour and it is validated in the countries participating in the project. In addition, this questionnaire will be common to all pilot studies in the different countries.

Secondly, based on the results of other studies, the **Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale** and the **DASS-21** tool were chosen, as self-esteem is a critical factor that affects the psychosocial adjustment of the individual, with evidence in the scientific literature linking it to anxiety, depression, stress and antisocial behaviour, and even suicidal tendencies.

Studies show that the practice of physical activity increases people's resilience and improves their physical and mental health, as well as favours the consolidation of the personality and helps to improve the level of personal self-esteem. It also improves problem-solving skills and develops the ability to self-regulate one's intentions for the future. Therefore, it was also decided to include **IPAQ-SF** to measure the practice of physical activity and **BIG FIVE-44** to determine whether personality had an influence on the study.

Furthermore, in all pilot studies of the project, the activities carried out will be evaluated according to the level of development of the resilience components (**social competence, troubleshooting, sense of purpose and future, cultural heritage** and **autonomy**). This aims to find out whether the proposed activities succeed in enhancing the resilience capacity in its different components.

Relationship between quality of life and perception of body image, as a resilient parameter, in former elite Volleyball players

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INTRODUCTION

- ✓ The connection between physical and sporting activity and psychophysical well-being leads to an increase in the number of practitioners and their plurality, as well as the different interests that guide sporting practices (Corrales-Salguero, 2009).
- ✓ Alonso et al. (2020) state that the practice of physical and sporting activity brings benefits in terms of improving emotional state, self-esteem and collective well-being.
- ✓ Body image is a multidimensional construct and refers to a person's perception and attitudes, including feelings, thoughts and behaviours regarding their own body and appearance (Niranjani and Vijayalakshmi, 2022).

The present work focuses on analyzing the relationship between the perception of body image and the quality of life of participants in federated volleyball competitions in the province of Jaén

METHODOLOGY

1. Design

- A descriptive, cross-sectional and single-measurement study was carried out.

2. Instrument

- In which a questionnaire was used to collect information on the perception of athletes' body image and quality of life, and its incidence on resilience.

- Surveys of team captains and coaches were also conducted to obtain additional data.

3. Sample

- A total of 199 athletes were studied, including 18 captains and 21 coaches.

RESULTS

1. It was found that athletes consider having a "good" level of quality of life, with a higher percentage in men than in women, with similar results in terms of the current state of well-being, with a higher percentage of men rating it as "good" compared to women.

2. The participating athletes highlighted the importance of maintaining a healthy lifestyle and pointed out that the personal experience lived in the years of sports practice plays a key role in its maintenance.

3. A direct relationship was found between the perception of quality and the body image of the subjects, supported by the statistical analysis carried out, which verifies that the perception of body image is associated with quality of life, and gender differences were observed in both aspects.

RESILIENCE

VOLEYBALL

CONCLUSIONS

The results suggest that both genders, although the male is greater, have a great capacity to adapt to situations, and their perception is that the experience they have lived has made them more resilient, especially in overcoming adversities throughout their lives. his personal and professional life, as well as the capacity for teamwork, leadership skills, and introspection.

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